

Synthesis and antimicrobial activity of some new 4-thiazolidinones derived from heterocyclic Schiff bases

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Ten new 4-thiazolidinones have been synthesized by condensation of heterocyclic Schiff bases (1a-e) with thioglycolic acid and thiomalic acid. All the compounds have been screened for their antibacterial and antifungal activities.

In view of diverse pharmacological activities of 4-thiazolidinones¹, ten new 4-thiazolidinone derivatives have been synthesized and screened for their biological activity.

Condensation of furan-2-aldehyde with five different heterocyclic amines, viz. 2-aminopyridine, 2-aminothiazole, 2-aminobenzothiazole, 2-amino-4-methylpyridine and 2-aminopyrimidine gave Schiff bases (1a-e), which on further condensation with thioglycolic acid and thiomalic acid yielded different 4-thiazolidinones (2,3a-e) (Scheme 1).

Experimental

All chemicals used were of A.R. grade. M.ps. were determined in open capillaries and are uncorrected. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Jasco report-100 spectrophotometer and ¹H NMR spectra (DMSO-*d*₆) on a Varian instrument (270 Hz) using TMS as internal standard. C, H and N were analyzed on a Carlo-Erba 1106 analyzer.

Schiff bases (1a-e): A mixture of furan-2-aldehyde (0.02 mol) and primary heterocyclic amine (0.02 mol) in ethanol (40 ml) was refluxed for 14–18 h. Excess of ethanol was then distilled off under reduced pressure. The resulting solid was washed with ethanol followed by ether and crystallized from benzene (yields 60–68%): **1a**, m.p. 120°; **b**, 129°; **c**, 123°; **d**, 132°; **e**, 138°; ν_{\max} 1615–1600 (C=N azomethine), 1510–1500 (furan ring bre. vibration); **1a** and **d**, 625–620 (in-plane pyridine ring deformation), 415–410 (out-of-plane pyridine ring deformation); **1b** and **c**, 690–685 (sym. C–S stretch.), 635–630 (asym. C–S stretch.); **1e**, 1565 cm^{-1} (pyrimidine ring bending vibration); **1a**, δ 3.54 (1H, s, CH=N), 7.70–7.78 (3H, m, furyl-H), 7.84–7.92 (4H, m, pyridyl-H); **b**, 3.56 (1H, s, CH=N), 7.32–7.40 (thiozoly-H), 7.71–7.78 (3H, m, furyl-H); **c**, 3.52 (1H, s, CH=N), 6.98–7.28 (4H, m, benzothiazolyl-H), 7.68–7.76 (3H, m, furyl-H); **d**, 2.38 (3H, s, pyridyl-CH₃), 3.45 (1H, s, CH=N),

Scheme 1

7.70–7.79 (3H, m, furyl-H), 7.82–7.92 (3H, m, pyridyl-H); **e**, δ 3.50 (1H, s, CH=N), 7.30–7.42 (3H, m, pyrimidyl-H), 7.75–7.84 (3H, m, furyl-H). All compounds gave satis-

factory C, H and N analyses.

4-Thiazolidinones (2,3a-e)² : A mixture of Schiff base (1a-e; 0.02 mol) and thioglycolic acid/thiomalic acid (0.02 mol) in dioxane (50 ml) was refluxed for 16–20 h. The excess of solvent was then removed under reduced pressure. The resulting residue was poured over crushed ice, set aside overnight in a refrigerator and centrifuged. The solid thus obtained was washed with 10% sodium bicarbonate solution and crystallized from methanol (yields 45–60%) : **2a**, m.p., 195°; **b**, 212°; **c**, 220°; **d**, 208°; **e**, 215°; **3a**, 245°; **b**, 260°; **c**, 272°; **d**, 255°; **e**, 252°; ν_{\max} 1720–1700 (C=O 4-thiazolidinone ring), 1225–1215 (C–S–C 4-thiazolidinone ring); **2a-e**, 2870–2860 (CH₂); **3a-e**, 3450–3400 (OH acid); **2,3a,d**, 635–620 (in-plane pyridine ring deformation), 420–410 (out-of-plane pyridine ring deformation); **2,3b** and **c**, 690–675 (sym. C–S stretch.), 635–625 (asym. C–S stretch.), 1480–1470 (C=N cyclic); **2,3e**, 1560–1555 cm⁻¹ (pyrimidine ring bending); **2a**, δ 3.12 (1H, s, CH–N), 3.70 (2H, s, S–CH₂), 7.77–7.80 (3H, m, furyl-H), 8.00–8.10 (4H, m, pyridyl-H); **b**, 3.24 (1H, s, CH–N), 3.62 (2H, s, S–CH₂), 7.38–7.46 (2H, m, thiazolyl-H), 7.80–7.90 (3H, m, furyl-H); **c**, 3.20 (1H, s, CH–N), 3.56 (2H, s, S–CH₂), 7.35–7.46 (2H, m, benzothiazolyl-H), 7.86–7.95 (3H, m, furyl-H); **d**, 2.27 (3H, s, pyridyl-CH₃), 3.50 (2H, s, S–CH₂), 3.22 (1H, s, CH–N), 7.80–7.90 (3H, m, furyl-H), 7.94–8.14 (3H, m, pyridyl-H); **e**, 3.15 (1H, s, CH–N), 3.64 (2H, s, S–CH₂), 7.32–7.44 (3H, m, pyrimidyl-H), 7.86–7.96 (3H, m, furyl-H); **3a**, 2.72 (2H, d, CH₂COOH), 4.90 (1H, t, CH–CH₂), 3.18 (1H, s, N–CH), 7.74–7.86 (3H, m, furyl-H), 7.96–8.14 (4H, m, pyridyl-H), 13.2 (1H, s, COOH); **b**, 2.70 (2H, d, CH₂COOH), 4.96 (1H, t, CH–CH₂), 3.12 (1H, s, N–CH), 7.35–7.46 (2H, m, thiazolyl-H), 7.66–7.78 (3H, m, furyl-H), 13.0 (1H, s, COOH); **c**, 2.68 (2H, d, CH₂COOH), 4.86 (1H, t, CH–CH₂), 3.24 (1H, s, N–H), 7.38–7.49 (4H, m, benzothiazolyl-H), 7.78–7.89 (3H, m, furyl-H), 12.8 (1H, s, COOH); **d**, 2.23 (3H, s, pyridyl-CH₃), 2.84 (2H, d, CH₂COOH), 3.26 (1H, s, CH–N), 4.94 (1H, t, CH–CH₂), 7.82–7.94 (3H, m, furyl-H), 8.03–8.14 (3H, m, pyridyl-H), 13.5 (1H, s, COOH); **e**, 2.75 (2H, t, CH₂COOH), 3.16 (1H, s, CH–N), 4.91 (1H, d, CH–CH₂),

7.34–7.46 (3H, m, pyrimidyl-H), 7.79–7.94 (3H, m, furyl-H), 13.8 (1H, s, COOH). All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

Antimicrobial activity : Antimicrobial activity of all the compounds was evaluated by adopting serial dilution (turbidimetric) method³ *in vitro* against the bacteria *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Escherichia coli* and the fungi *Asperigillus niger* and *Asperigillus flavus*.

Under identical conditions, the compounds showed minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) at micro mole level (μ M) : **1a**, 145.3; **b**, 70.2; **c**, 54.8; **d**, 134.4; **e**, 144.4; **2a**, 25.4; **b**, 24.8–14.4; **c**, 20.6; **d**, 24.0; **e**, 25.3; **3a**, 41.0–20.5, **b**, 40.2–20.1; **c**, 16.0; **d**, 39.3; **e**, 20.4 against both the bacteria. Similarly, the compounds showed MIC at micro level (μ M) : **1a**, 72.6; **b**, 70.2; **c**, 54.8–27.4; **d**, 67.2–134.4; **e**, 72.2; **2a**, 25.4; **b**, 12.4; **c**, 10.3; **d**, 24.0; **e**, 25.3; **3a**, 41.0; **b**, 20.1; **c**, 16.0; **d**, 19.9; **e**, 20.4–40.8 for both the fungi.

A comparative study of MIC values in general infers that the antimicrobial activity of Schiff bases is increased several times in the form of 4-thiazolidinones. The enhancement in the activity may be due to the addition of $\text{S-CH}_2\text{-C=O}$ moiety in the Schiff bases which forms a biologically active β -lactum ring. Further, among all the compounds, **3c** was found to be most active against both the bacteria. Similarly, compound **2c** was found most active against both the fungi. Rest of the compounds were found moderately active against all the organisms.

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